

Studies in the Cycloheptane Series : Part XXVII. Synthesis of 1-Carboxycycloheptyl-1- α -Alkyl/Arylalkyl Acetic and Succinic acids, their resolution into d- and l- forms and study of the effect of the solvents on the specific rotation

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Condensation of ethyl 1-cyanocycloheptyl-1- α -cyanoacetate with alkyl and arylalkyl halides in presence of sodium ethoxide or molecular sodium yields the respective ethyl 1-cyanocycloheptyl- α -alkyl/arylalkyl- α -cyanoacetates which on hydrolysis furnish the corresponding 1-carboxycycloheptyl-1- α -substituted acetic acids. Ethyl 1-cyanocycloheptyl-1- α -cyanoacetate has also been condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and the resulting diester on subsequent hydrolysis affords 1-carboxycycloheptyl-1- α -succinic acid. All these acids have been resolved into their enantiomers and the effect of various solvents on the specific rotations is reported.

IN continuation of our work on the chemistry of cycloheptane^{1,2}, the present paper describes the synthesis of a number of 1-carboxycycloheptyl-1- α -substituted acetic- and succinic acids.

Cycloheptanone on condensation with ethyl cyanoacetate gave ethyl cycloheptylidene- α -cyanoacetate which on treatment with potassium cyanide and subsequent acidification gave ethyl 1-cyanocycloheptyl-1- α -cyanoacetate (I). This ester was later condensed with methyl iodide, ethyl bromide, allyl iodide, benzyl chloride and ethyl bromoacetate in presence of sodium ethoxide or molecular sodium to yield the respective dicyanoesters (II), which on hydrolysis furnished the corresponding acids (III). All the above acids have been resolved with brucine into their enantiomorphs and it was observed that the racemates had higher melting point than either of the two active forms like the cyclohexane and cyclooctane analogues^{3,4}. The specific rotations of these acids in various solvents were taken and it was observed that the specific rotatory powers in different solvents increases with the decreasing value of the dielectric constant of the solvents⁵.

Experimental

Ethyl 1-cyanocycloheptyl-1- α -cyanoacetate (0.05 mole), prepared by condensing cycloheptanone with ethyl cyanoacetate and treatment with potassium cyanide followed by acidification, was added in small lots with shaking to cooled sodium ethoxide (sodium 0.05 mole and absolute ethanol 50 ml). Alkyl or arylalkyl halide (0.05 mole) was then added and the reaction mixture, after keeping overnight at room temperature refluxed until neutral (20 hr). After removal of ethanol, the residue was acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed, dried (Na₂SO₄), ether recovered and the residue on distillation gave the diesters (II), which are listed in Table 1. These diesters were separately dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid, the solution after keeping overnight at room temperature diluted with water until it became slightly turbid and refluxed on a sand-bath first gently (1 hr.) and then vigorously (3 hr). The dark coloured reaction products were diluted, cooled, extracted with ether and on working up in the customary manner, the acids (III) were obtained which are entered in Table 2.

TABLE 1—ETHYL 1-CYANOCYCLOHEPTYL-1- α -ALKYL/ARYLALKYL-1-CYANOACETATES

R	b.p./mm. °C	Yield %	n_D^{25}	Mol. formula	Found %		Requires %	
					C	H	C	H
Methyl	133-4/5	60.7	1.4780	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂	67.6	7.8	67.7	8.0
Ethyl	147/9	72.3	1.4670	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂	68.5	8.4	68.7	8.4
Allyl	156/4	63.2	1.4722	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂	69.8	7.5	70.0	7.7
Benzyl	155/6	65.4	1.4924	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂	73.8	7.3	74.0	7.4

TABLE 2—1-CARBOXYCYCLOHEPTYL-1- α -ALKYL/ARYLALKYL ACETIC ACIDS

R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Found %		Requires %		S-benzylisothiuronium Salt m.p. °C
				C	H	C	H	
Methyl	168	60	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ O ₄	61.1	7.8	61.2	8.0	134
Ethyl	170	60	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₄	63.2	8.5	63.2	8.7	142
Allyl	164	70	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₄	64.8	8.2	65.0	8.3	134
Benzyl	172	76.5	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₄	69.8	7.8	70.0	8.0	137

1-Carboxycycloheptyl-1- α -succinic acid (III; R = -CH₂COOH): To molecular sodium prepared from sodium (1.38 g; 0.06 mole) and toluene (40 ml), ethyl 1-cyanocycloheptyl-1- α -cyanoacetate (14.0 g; 0.06 mole) was added and the contents refluxed until the entire amount of sodium dissolved. The reaction mixture was cooled, ethyl bromoacetate (10.0 g; 0.06 mole) added and after keeping overnight at room temperature refluxed until neutral (18 hr). The contents were added to water and extracted with ether, the ethereal solution was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄), solvent removed and the residue on distillation gave *ethyl 1-cyanocycloheptyl-1- α -cyanosuccinate* b. p. 165°/5 mm. n_D^{25} 1.4820. (Yield 13.0 g; 67.7%). I. R. ν_{max}^{NaCl} 1710 cm⁻¹. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 7.4. C₁₇H₂₄O₄N₂ requires C, 64.0; H, 7.5%).

The above ester (12.9 g) was kept overnight with sulphuric acid (25 ml), water (15 ml) added and the mixture refluxed on a sand bath (35 hr). The reaction product was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water and aq. sodium carbonate (10%; 2×100 ml). The combined alkaline extracts were acidified, the oily deposit on cooling and scratching gave a solid, m. p. 166°; on crystallisation from chloroform-pet. ether *1-carboxycycloheptyl-1- α -succinic acid*, m. p. 168°, was obtained (Yield: 6.2 g; 62%). I. R. ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1700 cm⁻¹.

(Found: C, 55.8; H, 6.9. C₁₂H₁₈O₆ requires C, 56.0; H, 7.0%). Its *S-benzylisothiuronium salt* had m. p. 147°.

Resolution of dl-1- α -carboxycycloheptyl-1- α -succinic acid: 1-Carboxycycloheptyl-1- α -succinic acid (5.16 g; 0.02 mole) was mixed with brucine (17.2 g; 0.04 mole) and dissolved in boiling water (250 ml). The brucine salt (4.5 g) obtained after the fourth crystallisation was decomposed with dil. hydrochloric acid and the liberated acid extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and ether recovered. The solid so obtained had a rotation, α_D^{25} +30.0° (1 = 1/2; C = 1.0 g/100 ml); on repeated purification, the acid of maximum rotation +35.5° (1 = 1/2; C = 0.9 g/100 ml) was obtained.

TABLE 3—SPECIFIC ROTATION IN DEGREES OF 1-CARBOXYCYCLOHEPTYL-1- α -ALKYL/ARYLALKYL ACETIC ACIDS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

R	Methyl alcohol	Ethyl alcohol	Chloroform	Ethyl acetate
	$[\alpha]_D^{28}$	$[\alpha]_D^{28}$	$[\alpha]_D^{28}$	$[\alpha]_D^{28}$
Methyl	+22.0	+26.0	+46.4	+42.2
	-23.8	-25.6	-44.5	-40.0
Ethyl	+20.5	+28.4	+48.5	+40.0
	-22.6	-25.4	-49.5	-42.5
Allyl	+25.4	+30.5	+50.5	+37.5
	-27.0	-29.5	-45.5	-37.7
Carboxymethyl	+30.5	+32.4	+45.0	+35.5
	-28.5	-31.5	-42.8	-34.3
Benzyl	+28.4	+35.0	+50.7	+40.0
	-28.0	-32.0	-52.0	-42.8

Isolation of the laevo-isomer: The mother liquors from the above were combined, concentrated in vacuo to half its volume, cooled to 0° and the solid which separated out was filtered. This process was repeated twice, the resulting mother liquor was decomposed with dil. hydrochloric acid and the liberated acid extracted with ether. The ethereal solution on working up gave a solid which had a rotation of α_D^{25} -28.6° (1 = 1/2; C = 0.7 g/100 ml). On repeated crystallisation from benzene-pet. ether the maximum rotation of the acid was -34.3° (1 = 1/2; C = 0.75 g/100 ml) in ethyl acetate. Both the isomers had m. p. 167°.

References

- S. S. BHARGAVA and G. S. SAHARIA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 397; 1975, 13, 1100.
- V. K. CHHATWAL and G. S. SAHARIA, *Indian J. Chem.*, (in press).
- A. FREDGA and M. MATELL, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belge.*, 1953, 62, 47.
- G. S. SAHARIA and M. P. TYAGI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 601.
- B. K. SINGH, S. M. VERMA and S. R. K. MURTHY, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1956, 43, 21.